

Methodological component in the content of teaching the grammatical side of foreign language speech

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Annotation: This article considers methodological component in the content of teaching the grammatical side of foreign language speech at the university. The goals of teaching a foreign language are an important methodological category. The starting point in determining the strategic goal of education is the social order of society in relation to the younger generation.

Key word: Systematic reviews, evidence summary, clinical practice guidelines, bibliographic study, methodology.

An evidence summary may be considered as a type of rapid review in that the time frame for completion is expedited compared to more traditional methods of evidence synthesis such as systematic reviews. Although there is some debate over the definition of a rapid review, this term is most commonly used to define a methodology that follows aspects of systematic review methodology, with the omission of various steps to reduce the time and resources required. The term “evidence summary,” although broadly used, is poorly defined. The methodologies used in evidence summaries are likely to differ extensively, beyond simply omitting particular steps of the systematic review process. Although the broad purpose of systematic reviews, rapid reviews and evidence summaries is to facilitate evidence-based practice by summarizing evidence, the methodology, application, dissemination and target audiences may differ among these three types of resource.

An evidence summary includes different types of evidence such as experimental and observational studies, systematic reviews, and clinical practice guidelines. Systematic reviews typically take from six months to two years to complete, are predominantly published in peer-reviewed journals, and the format tends to be targeted more at academics or researchers. Rapid reviews, although not well-reported, appear to take anywhere from one week to six months to complete, are published as reports and increasingly in academic journals, and target a variety of audiences including

government agencies, health care professionals, patients, and researchers. Derivative products such as plain language or evidence summaries tend to target clinicians and policy makers; this review seeks to determine other methodological differences.

Another resource produced with the aim of facilitating evidence-based health care is clinical practice guidelines. A key difference between clinical practice guidelines and these three types of resources (evidence summaries, rapid reviews, and systematic reviews) is the additional layer of expert opinion or consensus that is combined with the highest level of evidence available to create recommendations for practice. Clinical practice guidelines are usually large documents covering multiple topics of care in a specific area, they are labor- and cost-intensive, and they are difficult to keep up-to-date (updated at arbitrary time points), especially in areas with an active research agenda. In contrast, an evidence summary is likely to be a short document (fewer than five pages) that is focused on a specific aspect of care and is regularly updated. Although the target audiences of evidence summaries and clinical practice guidelines are similar, the dissemination and methodologies are likely to differ substantially.

A number of literature review (often systematic review) derivative products are available such as BMJ Best Practice, UpToDate, and JBI evidence summaries. Each of these derivatives has the broad purpose of facilitating knowledge to action at the point of care; however, in most cases the methodologies of these derivative products are poorly reported, and therefore clinicians and policy makers must assume that the product is of high quality with no objective evaluation methods available. Dissemination also differs in that evidence summaries may be distributed to clinical points of care via electronic medical records, clinical decision support systems, or databases that are accessed from global publishers.

A bibliographic study described and evaluated the quality, rigor, and content of evidence-based practice point-of-care resources. The study assessed the quality of five main methodological components including search methodology, critical appraisal, hierarchical evidence inclusion, evidence grading, and whether expert opinion (if included) was identifiable. The study included 20 resources that present evidence for clinicians at the point of care, yet across these resources there was poor conceptual overlap on what constituted measures of quality; measures of internal validity were particularly lacking, and similar literature tends to focus on scope, breadth, and editorial control of content. Although these are important domains of quality, they are of unclear benefit in the quality assessment of evidence summaries. Given that quality assessment usually focuses on internal validity, it is likely that other methodological components

could contribute to evaluating the quality of an evidence summary and mapping of this literature is warranted.

Language teaching came into its own as a profession in the last century. Central to this process was the emergence of the concept of methods of language teaching. The method concept in language teaching—the notion of a systematic set of teaching practices based on a particular theory of language and language learning—is a powerful one, and the quest for better methods preoccupied teachers and applied linguists throughout the 20th century. Howatt (1984) documents the history of changes in language teaching throughout history, up through the Direct Method in the 20th century. One of the most lasting legacies of the Direct Method has been the notion of method itself.

Methodology in language teaching has been characterized in a variety of ways. A more or less classical formulation suggests that methodology links theory and practice. Within methodology a distinction is often made between methods and approaches, in which methods are held to be fixed teaching systems with prescribed techniques and practices, and approaches are language teaching philosophies that can be interpreted and applied in a variety of different ways in the classroom. This distinction is probably best seen as a continuum ranging from highly prescribed methods to loosely described approaches.

Last years the imperative need of using a foreign language appears in all areas of a science, manufacture and culture.

In present practice of teaching foreign languages there are some typical problems forcing the teacher to address to experience of the colleagues, to innovative ideas, to a science. Among these problems, difficulties and lacks of a traditional technique of teaching there are the following basic problems:

- Low authority of a subject because of shortages of a present technique of teaching.
- Low intensity of pupils' speech activity.
- Superficiality in forming of base skills and haste of transition from reproductive to productive kinds of work.
- Absence of good practical recommendations on elimination and the prevention of gaps in pupils' knowledge and skills.
- Weakness of existing system of appreciation of pupils' work.
- Spontaneity of a choice and application of evident support, their low didactic efficiency.

Researches of methods of teaching have shown, that all named problems will effectively solved, if we apply elaborations of various innovators for amplification of a traditional technique of teaching that can increase essentially quality of teaching foreign (in particular English) language.

Imperfection of the existing approach to teaching foreign language in the high school, which is focused only on communicative purposes to the detriment of such kinds of language activity as reading and the writing, that has led to the low level of knowing a foreign language of graduates of secondary school.

Importance and openness of the problem of effective teaching foreign languages have caused its topicality, and consequently the choice of a theme for the given research work.

It also has determined the aim of work: to distinguish the most rational techniques of teaching a foreign language which can be used in school.

The subject of this course paper is variety of methods and ways and their effectiveness of using in teaching a foreign language.

The object of research is the process of teaching and pupils who are the subjects of this teaching process.

In this work it is necessary to solve the following primary objectives:

- Theoretically to comprehend and approve in practice available approaches to teaching a foreign language in high school.
- To analyze the basic contents of a teaching material and principles of its organization in a rate of foreign language
- To compare suggested approaches and to choose the most comprehensible.

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